

Adaptive and Scalable Knowledge Management for Robotic Applications via Logic Languages

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Abstract—This work outlines a framework that combines knowledge representation systems with planning capabilities. It is based on four main pillars: • Automated knowledge extraction from natural language descriptions using Large Language Models (LLMs). • Generation of temporal plans for multi-robot systems using inference rules. • Automatic translation of plans into executable formalisms. • Runtime monitoring of the plan execution, learning from exceptions, and updating the knowledge-base dynamically.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the incredible progress made in the field of artificial intelligence (AI) every day, one of the greatest challenges is how to effectively manage the knowledge about the environment that humans and robots share. In this abstract, we are going to focus on: **Knowledge-base generation**: using Large Language Models (LLMs) to create a Knowledge Base (KB) written in Prolog to exploit its inference abilities. **Explainable plan generation**: the framework should provide plans that are explainable. **(Neuro-)probabilistic extension**: the framework must be able to work under uncertainty. **Learning from experience**: when some uncertainty is introduced, the framework should be able to change KB learning from the execution of the plan.

State-of-the-art knowledge management systems heavily rely on ontologies to ground information, especially common knowledge. However, ontologies are usually task-specific, and their creation is complex and time-consuming. Another important challenge for our work comes from the need for the system to adapt to real-time changes in the environment. The objectives of our framework are as follows I) *robustness*: the plan generated using the existing frameworks usually does not consider any of the theories behind planning and in particular probabilistic temporal planning; *handling partial knowledge*: at the best of our knowledge, no framework considers uncertainty in the KB; *multi-agent collaboration*: the existing frameworks do not directly address multi-agent systems. *visual input query*: none of the above frameworks considers the possibility of taking as input a series of images depicting what the agent should do, similar to the instructions to build a piece of furniture.

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Fig. 1: The structure of the framework.

II. CURRENT FRAMEWORK

In Figure 1, the general structure of the framework is shown. The framework is composed of many blocks that can be organized in the following macro blocks: i) **Knowledge management system**: it takes care of creating the KB and maintaining it. ii) **Planner**: it takes the KB and produces a feasible plan. iii) **Execution module**: it produces a BT that can then be executed calling the due APIs. iv) **Monitoring module**: it oversees the execution of the plan and provides the right information to the knowledge management system to update the KB.

Knowledge Management System. This module takes a natural language description of the environment, the actions and the task we want to accomplish and queries an LLM to create a Prolog KB. We use a few-shot learning by passing on a series of examples describing how we want the output to be organized. After calling the APIs and getting back a result, we enter a feedback loop in which we parse the output to check for some common mistakes, both semantic and syntactic. If the output is correct, then we incorporate it into the KB, otherwise we ask the LLM to regenerate the output minding to correct the detected errors. Similarly to the work of [1], we employ two LLMs, one for the generation of a high-level KB in which we incorporate actions and predicates that generically describe the environment and the agents' capabilities, while a second LLM is provided with the APIs that the agents expose, and it is responsible for mapping high-level actions to low-level ones. In Figure 1, a human is depicted, who has a twofold goal: I) provide the initial description, and II) update the KB based on the feedback loops. The idea is to automate the second step by checking for some common mistakes and automatically updating the description without the human-in-the-loop.

Fig. 2: In black, the causal relations between the different actions. In red, the duration constraints for the STN.

Fig. 3: An example of BT.

Planner. We exploit Prolog inference mechanics to find a series of actions in the KB, which let the system reach the final state. Prolog search is depth-first, meaning that it will find solutions that are probably sub-optimal, not to mention the complexity. To mitigate such a problem, we introduce a cap to the depth of the recursion. The list of actions that Prolog extracts represents the *total order plan*. Then we look for the achievers of the different actions, which means that we look for the causality relationships. This allows us to build a *partial-order plan* where some actions may be executed in parallel, as shown in black in Figure 2. Next, we add the temporal constraints over the durative actions, meaning that an end action must occur within a certain amount of time from the start action, as shown in red in Figure 2. By doing this, we extract a *STN*, the consistency of which can be checked by asserting the absence of negative cycles. Using a combination of partial-order planning and temporal planning, we can construct plans for multiple agents working together. Moreover, given the Prolog KB, it is possible to use inference to coordinate multiple heterogeneous agents.

Behaviour Trees. Once the STN has been built and verified, we proceed with the creation of a BT. Indeed, given the structure of the BT, it is easy to execute actions and especially to monitor the execution by inserting conditional nodes in the tree. The algorithm to transform STNs to BTs is described in much more detail in [2], but the general idea is the following. We start from the root node of the STN, and then we check the number of children that a node has. If it has more than one, then the children do not have a causal relationship and can be executed in parallel, i.e., we add a parallel control node to the BT. Instead, if the node has only one child, the control node will be sequential. We also check for the number of parents of a node: if there is more than one, then the node needs to wait for all the parents to have terminated before being able to execute. This procedure is repeated recursively until all nodes of the STN have been

inserted into the BT. In Figure 3, the BT corresponding to the STN shown in Figure 2 is depicted.

III. EXAMPLE APPLICATION

We have tested [3], [4] the system using the following scenario: we started from a configuration of $N_b > 1$ blocks placed on a table, either on the surface or already stacked, and by using $N_a > 1$ robotic arms we had to plan a sequence of actions so that the robots did not collide and the final action would have left us in a configuration that corresponded to the final goal. We assumed knowledge on the positions of the blocks and perfect execution on the agents side, e.g., when stacking two blocks the actions succeed in a perfect execution, and also the grip on the blocks is foolproof. As reported in [3], we used 3 different LLMs to create 10 pairs of initial and final states from the natural language description, while the KB regarding the actions that the agents could perform was hard-coded. The LLM that performed best was GPT-4, with 80% success rate, while GPT-3.5 and Bard performed at the same level with 40% success rate. In this case, the success rate is defined as the ability of the LLM to produce Prolog code that could be directly embedded in the framework and that would have not needed to be fixed by a human.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a comprehensive framework that integrates knowledge representation, planning, execution, and monitoring for multi-robot systems. Leveraging LLMs for knowledge extraction and Prolog for inference, the system generates temporal plans translated into executable formalisms. Future improvements include autonomous KB management, probabilistic planning, and enhanced monitoring for adaptive execution. The framework offers promise for automation in diverse industries, addressing challenges of robustness, uncertainty handling, multi-agent collaboration, and visual input queries.

An important aspect that we aim to improve is the addition of uncertainty in the KB. Indeed, at the moment, we assume that we know with precision the predicates of the KB, but this is not always the case, especially when we aim at integrating an autonomous process for the creation of the KB from vision and sensory data. In addition, we would like to consider alternative solvers to generate a plan, which can lead to (sub)optimal plans faster. While we want to retain the Prolog inference ability to ensure the correctness of the KB, we could extract a PDDL domain and problem from the KB and then use state-of-the-art solvers to enhance the framework abilities.

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